

Synthesis and characterization of complexes of cobalt(III) with pentadentate 1,2-propanediaminetetraacetic acid, 1,3-propanediaminetetraacetic acid and *trans*-1,2-cyclohexanediaminetetraacetic acid

N. Balasubramanian and V. Violet Dhayabaran*

PG & Research Department of Chemistry, Bishop Heber College, Tiruchirappalli-620 017, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : violetstaff@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 7 February 2005, revised 21 November 2005, accepted 2 December 2005

Abstract : The pentadentate complexes of cobalt(III) with stereospecific ligands 1,2-propanediamine tetraacetic acid (1,2-PDTA), 1,3-propanediaminetetraacetic acid (1,3-PDTA) and *trans*-1,2-cyclohexanediaminetetraacetic acid (*trans*-1,2-CyDTA) have been synthesized. Elemental analysis and spectral analysis including IR and ¹H NMR have been carried out. The presence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding is confirmed based on pK_a measurements. Number of molecules of water of crystallization has been determined from thermogravimetric analysis.

Keywords : Pentadentate ligands, cobalt(III) complexes, synthesis and characterization.

The coordination chemistry of complexes of cobalt(III), chromium(III) and rhodium(III) with edta-type ligands has received great attention in recent years¹. Cobalt(III) diaminocarboxylate complexes have been extensively studied^{2,3} from a number of view points including spectral, NMR, thermodynamic and kinetic behaviour⁴. The study of interaction of edta type ligands with the metal ions cobalt and copper has elicited much interest since they promote the interaction of nucleic acids with amino acids in biological system leading to the formation of ternary complexes^{5,6}. Crystallographic studies of hexadentate complex of Cu^{II} edta-type provides structural information of the complex⁷. The cobalt metal ion finds wide application in the field of nanotechnology in which formation of cobalt encapsulating nanotubes was investigated⁸ to carry out the reactions in a specially arranged closed cell at different temperatures. Multivalved carbon nanotubes along with carbon encapsulated cobalt nanoparticles were generated via catalytic disproportionation reaction. Complexes related to cobalt 1,2-PDTA, 1,3-PDTA have been synthesized and studied^{9,10} with respect to structure related to function. The special nature of the edta-type ligands viz. 1,2-PDTA, 1,3-PDTA and *trans*-1,2-CyDTA is, it includes changes in the diamine ring and structural changes in the carboxylate arm. The structural information for these complexes provide a better understanding of the influence of ligand configuration and conformation on metal(III) ions. The cobalt(III)-

PDTA and cobalt(III)-CyDTA complexes are found serving as useful models in the study of metalloproteins. Kinetics of formation of [Co(1,2-PDTA)]⁻ from the analogous pentadentate halo complexes have been studied and the function of active methyl group has been reported¹¹. It has been established that rotamer populations of cobalt(III) complexes calculated by vicinal and proton coupling constant analysis revealed the effect of non-covalent intra and interligand interactions¹².

To elucidate the role of structure of the ligands in complex formation and its spectral properties the present investigation has been undertaken. This paper will report the synthesis and characterization of the complex ions [Co(1,2-HPDTA)N₃]⁻, [Co(1,3-HPDTA)N₃]⁻ and *trans*-[(1,2-HCyDTA)N₃]⁻ which includes elemental analysis, and spectral analysis such as DTG, UV, IR and ¹H NMR. The data obtained is expected to provide fundamental information on the nature of the complex ions. The presence and absence of hydrogen bonding in these systems were inferred from pK_a measurements. DTG analysis was useful to ascertain the number of water of crystallization. NMR spectral data provides qualitative information concerning the type of protons of the complex ions which served as a supporting evidence for structural studies. The IR spectral data obtained for the complex ion was useful to diagonalise the linkages of the bonds and confirms the structure. The behaviour of low spin cobalt(III) complexes was viewed in the light of UV-spectral data.

The electronic transitions in the visible and high energy charge transfer regions were assigned for the complexes.

Results and discussion

Chemical (C, H, N) analysis confirms the stoichiometry: $[M(HL)N_3]^-$ where $M = Co^{III}$ and $L = 1,2\text{-PDTA}$, $1,3\text{-PDTA}$ or *trans*- $1,2\text{-CyDTA}$. The complexes are bluish violet in colour, stable, highly soluble in water and sparingly soluble in organic solvents.

Complexes of the formula $[Co(HY)N_3]^-$ where $Y = 1,2\text{-PDTA}$, $1,3\text{-PDTA}$ and $1,2\text{-CyDTA}$ exhibited an intense absorption band associated with three coordinated carboxylic groups at 1652 , 1629 and 1606 cm^{-1} respectively. They are abnormally broad and strong bands in these regions and they are unsymmetrical and it may be due to the overlapping of the expected band owing to the complexed and free carboxylate groups. The complexes also showed bands at 1230 , 1230 , 1241 cm^{-1} and they can be attributed for ionic carboxylate groups for the complex ions $[Co(1,2\text{-HPDTA})N_3]^-$, $[Co(1,3\text{-HPDTA})N_3]^-$ and $[Co(1,2\text{-HCyDTA})N_3]^-$ respectively. The presence of azido linkage to the metal ion was confirmed by the frequency values observed at 2045 , 2050 and 2045 cm^{-1} for the complex ions respectively. The bands at 1725 , 1675 and 1680 cm^{-1} can be accounted for the protonated carboxylic group of the complex ions. The results were in good agreement with the values reported earlier¹³ (Fig. 1).

1H NMR spectra of the complex ions provide qualitative information concerning the nature of protons. The labilities of individual metal-ligand bonds can be inferred from 1H NMR data, which is difficult to obtain by any other methods. Knowledge of this kind of information is useful in understanding the kinetics of the reaction. The complex ion, $[Co(1,2\text{-HPDTA})N_3]^-$ showed peaks at 1.6 , 2.54 , 3.7 , 3.81 and 8.4 ppm. The peak at 1.6 ppm can be assigned to the methyl group which is present at the backbone of the ligand in the ethylenediamine ring (E-ring). It is to be noted that no such peak is observed in other two systems. There are four acetate arms, out of four three arms were bonded to the metal ion and that results less strained complex. The peak at 3.81 can be accounted for the expected acetate protons which are coordinated to the metal ion. It would be expected that unbonded acetate proton would be different from bonded acetate proton. A peak at around 3.7 can be attributed for the same. The presence of ethylenic proton can be confirmed from the peak at 2.54 ppm. There is a small peak integrated for one proton at 8.4 ppm can be accounted from free carboxylic group proton.

Fig. 1. Ultraviolet-visible absorption spectra of $[Co(1,2\text{-HPDTA})N_3]^-$ in water.

Similarly $[Co(1,3\text{-HPDTA})N_3]^-$ ion showed peaks at 3.48 , 2.49 and 8.1 ppm they can be assigned for acetate proton, ethylenic proton and free carboxylic proton respectively.

In the case of $[Co(1,2\text{-HCyDTA})N_3]^-$ peaks were seen at 3.59 , 2.51 and 8.31 ppm. These peaks can be accounted for bonded acetate protons, methylene proton and free carboxylic acid proton.

The low-spin cobalt(III) octahedral complexes exhibit electronic transitions in the visible region with moderate intensity which are assigned as $d-d$ transition¹⁴, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$. Balasubramanian and Natarajan¹⁵ have examined the spectrum of the $[\text{Co}(\text{HEDTA})\text{N}_3]^-$ ion which showed only one ligand-field band and suggested that the other ligand-field band could not be observed as a separate band, because the intense charge transfer band, $\text{Co}^{\text{III}} \leftarrow \text{N}_3$, appearing at a relatively low energy region, might have masked the other weak ligand-field band. A similar observation is made in the spectrum of the complex ions $[\text{Co}(1,2\text{-HPDTA})\text{N}_3]^-$, $[\text{Co}(1,3\text{-HPDTA})\text{N}_3]^-$ and *trans*- $[\text{Co}(1,2\text{-HCyDTA})\text{N}_3]^-$. The three azido complexes synthesized showed a typical ligand-field band. The other ligand-field band is seen as a shoulder, hidden in the tail of the more intense charge transfer band. The results are in good agreement with those reported in the literature¹⁶.

The $\text{p}K_a$ values of the complex ion were determined by titrimetric method and found to be 3.75 and 3.65 and 3.05 for the complex ions $\text{Co}(1,2\text{-HPDTA})\text{N}_3^-$, $[\text{Co}(1,3\text{-HPDTA})\text{N}_3]^-$ and *trans*- $[\text{Co}(1,2\text{-HCyDTA})\text{N}_3]^-$ under a given set of operating conditions.

A hydrogen bridge can be visualized as a proton of free COOH group shared by two lone pairs of electrons of nitrogen N_3 group. As a consequence of the hydrogen bridge, the covalent bond in the proton-donor group gets weakened and hence the characteristics of the proton acceptor group get varied. Experiments were conducted with a view to determining the influence of both ionic strength and temperature on the $\text{p}K_a$ values. The $\text{p}K_a$ values of the complex ion, $[\text{Co}(1,2\text{-HPDTA})\text{N}_3]^-$ or $[\text{Co}(1,3\text{-HPDTA})\text{N}_3]^-$ is 3.75 or 3.65 respectively. It is found slightly higher than *ca.* 3. Such a slight higher value can be accounted for in terms of some influence exerted by the azido ligand on the proton of the CH_2COOH group. An analysis of the data reveals that both ionic strength and the temperature have little influence on the $\text{p}K_a$ value indicating the absence of intermolecular hydrogen bridge and also the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bridge in these complexes. The $\text{p}K_a$ value of the azido complex ion *trans*- $[\text{Co}(1,2\text{-HCyDTA})\text{N}_3]^-$ is found to be 3.05. It is in good agreement with the $\text{p}K_a$ value of the complex ion $[\text{Co}(1,2\text{-HPDTA})\text{Br}]^-$ viz. 3.0 reported earlier¹⁷. The structure of $[\text{Co}(1,2\text{-HPDTA})\text{Br}]^-$ has already been confirmed¹⁶.

Derivative thermogravimetric analysis was made to determine the number of molecules of the water of crystallization in each complex. The results suggest the mo-

lecular formulae of the complex ions as $[\text{Co}(1,2\text{-HPDTA})\text{N}_3] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Co}(1,3\text{-HPDTA})\text{N}_3] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Co}(1,2\text{-HCyDTA})\text{N}_3] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical grade.

IR spectra of the complexes were recorded on IF S66U IR spectrometer in the range 4000–200 cm^{-1} using KBr discs. The frequencies corresponding to protonated, coordinated and ionic carboxylate ions were noted. They exhibit strong broad bands at 1652, 1629, 1606 cm^{-1} and weak bands at 1725, 1675, 1680 cm^{-1} and additional bands at 1230, 1230, 1241 cm^{-1} for the complex ions $[\text{Co}(1,2\text{-HPDTA})\text{N}_3]^-$, $[\text{Co}(1,3\text{-HPDTA})\text{N}_3]^-$, $[\text{Co}(1,2\text{-HCyDTA})\text{N}_3]^-$ respectively. The ultraviolet-visible absorption spectra of the complexes were observed on 5501 CECIL spectrophotometer using a quartz cell of 10 mm path length. Each of the complex ions showed two charge transfer bands and one visible absorption band. The wavelength of absorption maximum along with ϵ values are given as follows. $[\text{Co}(1,2\text{-HPDTA})\text{N}_3]^-$ showed the charge transfer bands at 225 nm, 315 nm and one visible absorption band at 560 nm with the ϵ values 11815 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$, 6805 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ and 220 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ respectively. Similarly $[\text{Co}(1,3\text{-HPDTA})\text{N}_3]^-$ showed bands at 219, 319 and 570 nm with ϵ values 12203 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$, 4434 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$, 181 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. Similarly *trans*- $[\text{Co}(1,2\text{-HCyDTA})\text{N}_3]^-$ showed bands at 214, 311 and 551 nm with ϵ values 21980 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$, 6310 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$, 237 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra were recorded at JEDL GSX 406 model FT NMR spectrometer. Acid dissociation constants were determined by titrimetric method using a digital pH meter Elico Private Ltd., India.

General procedure for synthesis of complexes :

An alkali solution of the ligands 1,2-propanediaminetetraacetic acid or 1,3-propanediaminetetraacetic acid or *trans*-1,2-cyclohexanediaminetetraacetic acid is mixed with an aqueous solution of cobalt(II) chloride solution with constant stirring. A known weight of solid sodium azide was added in small portion along with the addition of hydrogen peroxide solution for a period of three hours. Temperature and pH of the reaction mixture was maintained below 5 °C and around 4 respectively. The progress of the reaction could be noticed by observing the colour change from pink to red. The process of stirring was continued for a further period of about two hours. The resulting reaction mixture was then transferred to a beaker containing dry acetone and this caused a sepa-

ration of bluish violet coloured solid. The crude product was dissolved in a minimum amount of water and treated with dry acetone. The process of purification was repeated till pure violet coloured crystals of the complex separated, dried under reduced pressure.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr Marcus Diepen Boominathan, Principal, Dr T Venkatachalam, Head, Department of Chemistry, Bishop Heber College, Tiruchirappalli for their encouragement, support and UGC, New Delhi for research grant.

References

- 1 B E Douglas and D J Radanovic, *Coord Chem Rev*, 1993, **124**, 139
- 2 H Ogino, *Bull Chem Soc Jpn*, 1965, **38**, 771
- 3 F P Dwyer and F L Garvan, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1959, **81**, 2955
- 4 R G Wilkins and R E Yelin, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1970, **92**, 1191
- 5 H Sigel, B E Fisher and E Farkas, *Inorg Chem*, 1983, **22**, 925
- 6 H Sabat, K A Satyshur and M Sundaralingam, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1983, **105**, 976
- 7 D J Radanovic, T Ama, D M Guresic, D M Ristanovic, D D Radanovic and H Kauaguchi, *Bull Chem Soc Jpn*, 2000, **73**, 2283
- 8 R K Rana, Xu Xn, Y Yeshuru and A Gedanken, *J Phys Chem*, 2002, **106**, 4079
- 9 U Rychlewska, M I Djuran, M M Vasojevic, D O Radanovic, V M Ristanovic and D J Radanovic, *Inorganica Chimica Acta* 2002, **328**, 218
- 10 U Rychlewska, D D Radanovic, M D Dimitrijevic, D M Ristanovic, M M Vasojevic and D J Radanovic, *J Polyhedron*, 2001, **20**, 2523
- 11 K Swaminathan and D H Busch, *J Inorg Nucl Chem*, 1961, **20**, 159
- 12 D J U Miodragovic¹, S M Milosavljevic¹, M J Malinar¹, N Todorovic² and N Jurani³, *J Stereochem*, 2002, **7**, 375
- 13 K Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 3rd ed., John Wiley and Sons Inc., New York, 1978
- 14 P Natarajan and J F Endicott, *J Phys Chem*, 1973, **77**, 2049
- 15 N Balasubramanian and P Natarajan, *Indian J Chem, Sect A*, 1995, **34**, 481
- 16 K Swaminathan and D H Busch, *Inorg Chem*, 1962, **1**, 256
- 17 M H Evans, B Grossman and R G Wilkins, *Inorg Nucl Chem Lett*, 1974, **10**, 553